

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON HOTEL SERVICES DURING GLOBAL HEALTH CRISIS

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Abstract

COVID-19 is one of the most difficult challenges organizations have faced in the previous years. The Philippines' hotel industry is facing previously unheard-of difficulties as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic's lasting impacts. The study aimed to assess the level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in the areas of food and beverage, front office, and housekeeping as the basis for a customer service action plan. Likewise, it explored the challenges encountered by hotels during a global health crisis. The study used a descriptive-quantitative research design using a survey. The respondents of this study were the 211 guests of the nine DOT-accredited hotels. Convenience sampling was employed. An online software package for the analysis of statistical data was used to obtain the mean and standard deviation for the level of customer satisfaction; frequency and percentage were used in the challenges encountered because of their clarity in expressing quantitative analysis between variables. The findings of the study indicate guests' very high level of satisfaction with hotel services in all areas (food and beverage, housekeeping, and front office). In conclusion, the respondents perceived a very high overall level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in the areas of front office, food and beverage, and housekeeping.

Keywords: Business and Management, Global Health Crisis, Customer Satisfaction, Hotel Services, Front Office, Food and Beverage, Housekeeping, Descriptive-quantitative, Philippine Hotels.

Introduction

The World Health Organization designated the COVID-19 outbreak to be a global pandemic on March 12, 2020. In the first quarter of 2020, foreign visitor arrivals decreased by 22% as a result of travel restrictions and lockdowns imposed by the majority of countries. This was expected to cause a loss of US\$80 billion in worldwide tourism receipts (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2020). Travel restrictions and government-issued orders to stay at home resulted in a substantial decline in hotel occupancy and revenue (Gursoy & Chi, 2020).

The pandemic has had a notable impact on hotel patron satisfaction, with service quality being the primary issue during the pandemic (Song et al., 2022). Throughout the post-COVID era, hotels in the five Asia-Pacific countries of China, Indonesia, India, Malaysia, and Thailand have made an effort to draw guests and improve their quality of service. There are several reasons for this, including the ability to compare hotels to get insight from their best practices and refine their approach. To comprehend how effective hotel strategies are, it is also necessary to grasp consumers' perspectives (Ray & Ma, 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic's long-term effects pose unprecedented challenges to the Philippines' hotel sector. Restrictions on both domestic and international travel have decreased demand, causing a severe decline in occupancy rates and revenue (Lopez, 2021). In Negros Occidental, the Provincial Tourism Office reported that 2,637 employees in the tourism industry were displaced because of the coronavirus disease (Covid-19) pandemic. There were 1,218 affected workers from accommodation facilities. However, the accommodation facilities must strictly adhere to the minimum health standard protocols. In compliance with Department of Tourism guidelines, resorts and hotels are allowed to reopen under general community quarantine (GCQ) and modified general community quarantine (MGCQ) status. Moreover, due to the coronavirus pandemic, two hotels in Bacolod, Negros Occidental, have temporarily closed (Centina, 2020).

Thus, this study aimed to assess the level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in Negros Occidental in the areas of front office, food and beverage, and housekeeping. Likewise, it aimed to determine the challenges encountered by hotels during a global health crisis. The findings provided a baseline for a customer service action plan that hotel management, tourism agencies, and future researchers could utilize.

Literature Review

Global health crisis. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) labeled the coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak a pandemic that cost hundreds of thousands of human lives globally and caused disturbance to economies and communities. Tourism came to an end in March 2020 as a result of extensive limitations on public meetings and communal mobility, as well as travel bans that affected over 90% of the world's population. According to early evidence, the consequences of accommodation, cruises, and air travel bans have been severe. Early United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) projections for 2020 indicate that foreign arrivals may decline by 20 to 30% from 2019 levels, although these figures are quite tentative. According to Gössling et al. (2020), tourism is particularly susceptible to pandemic preventive measures due to its restricted mobility and social distancing.

Customer satisfaction with hotel services. For management, an important level of customer service must be a measurable result. Customer service is providing service to customers before, during, and after a purchase (Ndiba & Mbugua, 2018). Thus, it is crucial to look for methods to improve hotel services and make recommendations on how to handle the delivery of particular services that can raise client satisfaction and promote return business. Customer satisfaction is a key success factor in the tourist sector, and hotels can only stay competitive by meeting the expectations of their patrons (Mohammed & Rashid, 2018).

Front office. In the study by Chalupa and Chadt (2021), the researchers interviewed hotel and front office managers on topics of communication with guests and issues like inefficiencies in employee approach towards COVID-19. Findings showed that employees are unprepared for critical situations and need training on proper soft skills. This is concurred by Mankame (2021) that competence significantly affects negative impressions in distinguishing the service suppliers' attributes that impact guests' impressions. Also, friendliness and service manners significantly have a positive impact, and both positive and negative impacts significantly influence guest satisfaction with the registration experience in the hotel front office.

Food and beverage. Following the COVID-19 crisis, food and beverage aspects are no longer the only factors to consider; various features relating to COVID-19 prevention efforts have piqued tourists' attention. Tourists prioritize additional services linked to hygiene, safety, and social distancing measures, particularly during the COVID-19 crisis (Nilashi et al., 2021). Hygiene and cleanliness in different sectors of food and beverage manufacturing and service in the hospitality business, through effective and efficient service delivery, may enhance client satisfaction and retention (Lal, 2022). Today's scenarios focus on the hospitality industry developing innovative technologies, innovation, and environment-friendly services, which will help increase customer satisfaction. Factors like physical environment, entertainment facilities, hygiene, and cleanliness have become more popular than food quality (Kumar & Bhatnagar, 2017).

Housekeeping. Based on their study of hotels in Kolkata, India, Kumar et al. (2021) found that hotels require strict regulations to enforce effective COVID protocols. The authors also believe that in the post-COVID age, housekeeping personnel will be the most valuable resource since guests are concerned about hotel hygiene and safety (Kumar et al., 2021). Even after the virus peaks have passed and the hotel has reopened safely, the worry of infection will persist, necessitating guest faith and confidence (Sharma et al., 2021).

Challenges. The global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is being felt in company revenues, operations, and management policies. The tourism and hospitality industries are vulnerable to epidemics and should implement proper crisis and risk management protocols. In addition, when visiting a new destination, travelers are more concerned about potential health concerns. As a result, hotel management must ensure that they follow the WHO's and local authorities' recommended best practices (Nilashi et al., 2021).

Research Methods

Research design. This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative research design using a survey. A descriptive design does not take into account possible causes and effects because it gathers data on variables without altering the context or modifying any variables (Murphy-Reyes, 2017). When gathering and analyzing data, quantitative research places a strong emphasis on numbers and figures. The time and effort the researcher would have needed to describe his findings are cut down when statistical data are used for the research descriptions and analysis. Data (numbers, percentages, and measurable statistics) can be computed and handled by a computer using statistical online software packages, which can save a significant amount of time and money (Daniel, 2016).

Respondents. The respondents of this study were the 211 guests of the nine (9) DOT-accredited hotels located in the north, center, and southern areas of the province of Negros Occidental. These selected DOT-accredited hotels were based on the Department of Tourism (DOT) release of the updated accredited hotels authorized to operate for 2021. In determining the respondents, convenience sampling (also known as availability sampling) was used to select participants based on their ready availability or convenience.

Research instrument. A two-part researcher-made questionnaire was employed in the study: Part 1 contained questions on customer satisfaction in the three areas or departments of the hotel: food and beverage, front office, and housekeeping; it consisted of 37 items for assessing customer satisfaction with hotel services in Negros Occidental, which hotel guests answered. Part 2 contained questions on the challenges encountered; there were 21 items assessing the challenges encountered by guests at the hotel during the global health crisis, which the hotel guests answered.

Data collection procedure. Prior to the research questionnaire being distributed, the researcher notified the Negros Occidental Tourism Division, the Department of Tourism Western Visayas, and a few of the participating cities' tourism offices of the conduct of the study. The researcher also obtained an ethics clearance from the university and an endorsement letter. Similarly, through the hotel administration, the researcher obtained approval from the hoteliers to carry out the study on the visitors.

Data analysis procedure. Descriptive analysis was used to analyze and interpret customer satisfaction with hotel services and challenges during the global health crisis. An online software package used for the analysis of statistical data was used to obtain the mean and standard deviation for the level of customer satisfaction; frequency and percentage were used to identify the challenges encountered because of their clarity in expressing quantitative analysis between variables.

Ethical considerations. The researcher ensured that the study adhered to the ethical norms set forth by the Philippine Health Research Ethics Board (PHREB) by addressing the broad concepts of respect for person, fairness, and beneficence.

Findings and Discussion

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services

The overall level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in the areas of front office, food and beverage, and housekeeping, denoting a very satisfied result from the respondents ($M=4.61$, $SD=0.43$). Particularly, the housekeeping service obtained the highest mean score ($M=4.68$, $SD=0.40$), denoting a very satisfied result. This is followed by front office ($M=4.62$, $SD=0.40$) and food and beverage ($M=4.52$, $SD=0.50$).

The findings demonstrate that customer views of the facilities positively impacted their level of satisfaction, with the employees and business organization as facilitating factors (Baquero, 2023). Furthermore, the findings show that the implications of affective evaluation and cognitive effort on customer satisfaction are mediated by hotels' crisis response plans (Yu et al., 2023).

All hotel departments have experienced a complete transformation in operations due to the pandemic and other factors. In order to maintain service standards and adhere to the current pandemic's norms and requirements, housekeeping is now crucial (Kumar et al., 2021). Given that the pandemic has increased the responsibilities and challenges for the housekeeping department, cleanliness and hygiene are fundamentally important to both guests and hotels. In general, the housekeeping department is in charge of the hotel's cleanliness and safety, and they are required to abide by all regulations pertaining to the staff's and visitors' personal hygiene and safety. The findings suggest that housekeeping adheres to all room cleaning guidelines established by the Ministry or Department of Health (Sadhale, 2021).

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services in terms of Front Office

The level of customer satisfaction with hotel services of hotels in the area of front office which is interpreted as very satisfied ($M=4.62$, $SD=0.40$). The items "The hotel's front office staff are friendly and courteous" ($M=4.74$, $SD=0.51$) and "The hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the front office operating procedures to help their employees and guests" ($M=4.74$, $SD=0.50$) obtained the highest mean rated as very satisfied. Meanwhile, "The hotel provides luggage assistance" ($M=4.50$, $SD=0.66$) obtained the lowest mean, which was rated very satisfied.

This implies that the front office staff has effectively communicated and implemented health and safety protocols, ensuring the well-being of guests during the crisis. The guests experience positive and quality services, including check-in, check-out, and concierge assistance, and how the staff efficiently handles the activities of the front office.

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services in the Area of Housekeeping

The level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in housekeeping is very satisfied ($M=4.52$, $SD=0.50$). Particularly, "The hotel has adopted health and safety regulations as part of the housekeeping operating procedures to assist their personnel and visitors" ($M=4.72$, $SD=0.51$) obtained the highest mean, which was interpreted as very satisfied. The result revealed the lowest ($M=4.36$, $SD=0.82$), "The hotel has housekeeping turn down service at night," which was also very satisfied. This implies that the customers are very satisfied with the housekeeping services provided by the hotel. Guests are satisfied with the hotel's commitment to health and safety in housekeeping operations.

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services in the Area of Food and Beverage

The level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in the area of food and beverage is very satisfied ($M=4.68$, $SD=0.40$). Particularly, "The hotel's food and beverage staff are friendly and courteous and provide fast services" ($M=4.76$, $SD=0.46$) reflected the highest mean, followed by "The hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the food and beverage operating procedures to help their employees and guests," ($M=4.76$, $SD=0.52$) which are all interpreted as very satisfied.

Customer satisfaction is influenced by both positive and negative emotions related to the perceived quality of service provided by the provider. Service standards strengthen customer relationships with the businesses they patronize. In a restaurant that meets their expectations for how they want to be served, customers expect

promptness, friendliness, and excellent service (Abdullah et al., 2022). Overall customer satisfaction is determined by service qualities, which have been evaluated using aspects related to the menu and foods. In addition, factors like equipment, conformance levels, and the image of the product or destination were taken into account, as well as characteristics like price, cleanliness, safety, responsiveness, dependability, and serviceability (Zibarzani et al., 2022). Features like mask policies, safety, and social distancing are valued equally to characteristics that were once more prevalent, like overall experience, food quality, and service (Kostromitina et al., 2021).

Challenges Encountered by Hotels during a Global Health Crisis

The top three challenges encountered by hotels during the global health crisis. These are: the hotels have no area for symptomatic guests (12.80%), hotel screening on guest and travel history using the checklist provided by the DOH (12.30%), and how the hotel provides guests with reminder cards (e.g., no food sharing, proper disposal of used PPE, mingling with occupants, and proper handwashing) (10.40%). Nevertheless, based on the findings, there are no significant issues or concerns with hotel operations.

The emergence of COVID-19 has changed how organizations operate, and things will never be the same again after the pandemic. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the increased demand for crisis response and management put leaders in all organizations to the test. Fear is a powerful motivator for leaders to act quickly to ensure the safety and security of their people and organizations. Crisis leadership is critical in determining whether crisis management and response succeed or fail (Promsri et al., 2021).

Findings and Conclusion

The findings of the study indicate that guests have a very high level of satisfaction with hotel services in all areas (food and beverage, housekeeping, and front office). Particularly, the housekeeping service obtained the highest mean score, denoting a very high satisfaction result. This is followed by front office, food, and beverage.

Particularly, in the front office sub-areas, the results reveal a very high level of satisfaction, notably wherein the hotel's front office staff are friendly and courteous, and the hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the front office operating procedures to help their employees and guests. Moreover, in the housekeeping sub-areas, the results reveal a very high level of satisfaction in terms of the hotel's adoption of health and safety regulations as part of the housekeeping operating procedures to assist their personnel and visitors and how the hotel has housekeeping turn down service at night. Also, in the food and beverage sub-areas, the results reveal a very high level of satisfaction in terms of the friendly and courteousness of the food and beverage staff, their ability to provide fast services, and how the hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the food and beverage operating procedures to help their employees and guests.

Nevertheless, based on the findings, there are no significant issues or concerns with hotel operations. The only identified top three challenges encountered by hotels during the global health crisis are: some of the hotels have no area for symptomatic guests, hotel screening on guests and travel history using the checklist provided by the DOH, and how the hotel provides guests with reminder cards (e.g., no food sharing, proper disposal of used PPE, mingling with occupants, and proper handwashing).

In conclusion, the respondents perceived a very high overall level of customer satisfaction with hotel services in the areas of front office, food and beverage, and housekeeping. The findings demonstrated that customer views on these aforesaid hotel services positively impacted their level of satisfaction. All hotel departments have experienced a complete transformation in operations due to the pandemic and other factors due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the findings also imply that customer satisfaction is also ensured by the effective crisis response plans and strategies by the hotels, and compliance with the safety standards established by the local government and its medical partners.

The findings of the research demonstrate that it is essential for the hotel's front-desk personnel to uphold environmental sustainability, health, safety, and cleanliness standards in response to guests' growing demands for personal interaction with employees. Moreover, hotel guests characterize employee behavior to be "friendly" and "helpful." Indeed, the hallmarks of excellent service have been characterized as promptness, friendliness, and courtesy.

Moreover, in terms of housekeeping, it is concluded that guests are particularly satisfied with the hotel's commitment to health and safety in housekeeping operations. Housekeeping will be the bedrock of security, as cleanliness is critical to safety. A vital component of the hospitality industry is cleaning hotel rooms. The pandemic has increased awareness, so hotel staff will be more scrutinized about what constitutes a clean and safe room. The COVID-10 pandemic situation is expected to make hotel customers overly sensitive to the hygiene condition of the facility, not only for their pre-visit perception or behavior but also for their post-visit perception or behavior.

In addition, hygiene and food safety are the primary concepts in service delivery in the area of food and beverage. This also includes other factors like cleanliness, responsiveness, dependability, and serviceability of food and beverage services. In order to provide hotel guests with happiness and satisfaction during their consumption, the food and beverage department must satisfy them both physically and mentally. The results imply that it is important that staff members undergo regular training in areas such as food safety, technology, product knowledge, service standards, and cleanliness.

Lastly, there are not any significant issues or concerns with hotel operations. The results imply that crisis leadership was employed by hotel leaders. Leaders in every organization were put to the test during the COVID-19

pandemic due to the greater need for crisis response and management. The results imply that hotel managers have the capability to transform crises into opportunities to promote organizational resilience and the successful recovery of business operations.

Limitation and Further Research

Accommodation establishments are compelled to close temporarily due to this unforeseen circumstance brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Only the 13 Bacolod City hotels with DOT accreditation were the initially selected respondents in the study. Despite the Department of Tourism's (DOT) Regional Director's endorsement, the undersigned's request was not granted by 12 out of thirteen companies on the basis of guest confidentiality, and the hotel operations were converted into quarantine facilities. This leads to changes in both the study's location and the method of sampling employed. The data collected were restricted to a small number of guests because the study was carried out during a pandemic, and there were few visitors to the hotels. Of the twelve (12) DOT-accredited hotels in total, nine (9) of them responded.

The findings could pave the way for future researchers to conduct a continuous search of hotels in Negros Occidental without health crisis guidelines during a pandemic, as well as assess hotel resiliency during a global health crisis. Future researchers may also focus on customer satisfaction in other hotel departments, such as engineering and maintenance, sales and marketing, safety and security, and information technology. In addition, future researchers may study customer satisfaction in resorts with similar areas of concern and restaurants with no health guidelines during a pandemic.

Tables and Figures

Tables

Table 1.

Distribution of Hotel Guests

Hotel	f	%
A	18	8.5
B	21	10.0
C	22	10.4
D	50	23.7
E	25	11.8
F	13	6.2
G	12	5.7
H	12	5.7
I	38	18.0
Total	211	100.0

Table 2.

Overall Summary of Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services

Areas	M	SD	Int.
Front Office	4.62	0.40	VS
Food and Beverage	4.52	0.50	VS
Housekeeping	4.68	0.40	VS
Overall	4.61	0.43	VS

Note: Very Satisfied (VS) - 4.21 - 5.00; Satisfied (S) - 3.41 - 4.20; Slightly Satisfied (SS) - 2.61 - 3.40; Not Satisfied (NS) - 1.81 - 2.60; Very Unsatisfied (VU) - 1.00 - 1.80

Table 3.

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services in the Area of Front Office

Items	M	SD	Int
1. The hotel's front office staff are friendly and courteous.	4.74	0.51	VS
2. The hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the front office operating procedures to help their employees and guests.	4.74	0.50	VS
3. The hotel has a fast completion of pre-registration information during the booking process.	4.67	0.53	VS
4. The hotel offers to arrange transfer services.	4.67	0.52	VS
5. The hotel's front desk reservation system has updated information related to guest service.	4.65	0.54	VS
6. The hotel delivers minimal waiting time for check-in.	4.63	0.57	VS
7. The hotel responds to guest complaints immediately.	4.63	0.54	VS
8. The hotel has protocols to deliver a minimal waiting time for check-out.	4.62	0.54	VS
9. The hotel has a reception service available 24 hours.	4.62	0.62	VS
10. If complaints cannot be resolved to guest satisfaction, the hotel gives complimentary/discounts for bad service.	4.61	0.59	VS
11. The hotel offers several payment options.	4.60	0.60	VS
12. The hotel provides a front desk safety deposit box.	4.60	0.61	VS
13. The hotel solicits guest feedback.	4.54	0.68	VS
14. The hotel uses new technology for easy guest check-in and check-out.	4.52	0.63	VS
15. The hotel provides luggage assistance.	4.50	0.66	VS
Overall	4.62	0.40	VS

Note: Very Satisfied (VS) - 4.21 - 5.00; Satisfied (S) - 3.41 - 4.20; Slightly Satisfied (SS) - 2.61 - 3.40; Not Satisfied (NS) - 1.81 - 2.60; Very Unsatisfied (VU) - 1.00 - 1.80

Table 4

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services in the Area of Housekeeping

Items	M	SD	Int
1. The hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the housekeeping operating procedures to help their employees and guests.	4.72	0.51	VS
2. The hotel's housekeeping department has cleaning schedules that are in place.	4.62	0.57	VS
3. There are no intrusive noises from the other rooms.	4.61	0.57	VS
4. Electronic devices and reliable, wireless internet connectivity.	4.61	0.63	VS
5. The hotel rooms are precooled for arrival.	4.56	0.62	VS
6. The hotel has room service for 18-24 hours.	4.47	0.68	VS
7. The hotel provides a small safety deposit box in each room, which is functional and securely bolted.	4.41	0.83	VS
8. The hotel has an electronic key card locking system.	4.40	0.94	VS
9. The hotel provides the in-room collection with extensive regional information on what to see and do for tourists.	4.39	0.85	VS
10. The hotel has housekeeping turndown service at night.	4.36	0.82	VS
Overall	4.52	0.50	VS

Note: Very Satisfied (VS) - 4.21 - 5.00; Satisfied (S) - 3.41 - 4.20; Slightly Satisfied (SS) - 2.61 - 3.40; Not Satisfied (NS) - 1.81 - 2.60; Very Unsatisfied (VU) - 1.00 - 1.80

Table 5

Level of Customer Satisfaction with Hotel Services in the Area of Food and Beverage

Items	M	SD	Int
1. The hotel's food and beverage staff are friendly and courteous and provide fast service.	4.76	0.46	VS
2. The hotel has implemented health and safety protocols as part of the food and beverage operating procedures to help their employees and guests.	4.75	0.52	VS
3. The hotel's floor, walls, and ceilings of the food premises are adequately cleaned.	4.74	0.50	VS
4. The hotel provides adequate handwashing facilities, including soap and paper towels.	4.71	0.50	VS
5. The hotel has a sufficient ventilation system to effectively remove fumes, smoke, steam, and vapors from the food premises.	4.69	0.54	VS
6. The hotel has adequate toilet facilities, which are maintained nuisance-free, away from food service.	4.69	0.49	VS
7. The hotel food and beverages utilize clean utensils (e.g., scoops, spatulas, or other food dispensing devices).	4.68	0.54	VS
8. The hotel's food and beverage utilizes clean plastic gloves to minimize direct hand contact with food.	4.68	0.54	VS
9. Eating or drinking utensils are maintained in good condition.	4.65	0.58	VS
10. The hotel has an implementation of measures to keep the area from animals and pests.	4.64	0.58	VS
11. There is regular maintenance for fixtures, fittings, and equipment to be in good condition.	4.62	0.58	VS
12. The hotel provides a mechanism or platform for visitors to give feedback on food and beverage service quality.	4.54	0.67	VS
13. Overall	4.68	0.40	VS

Note: VS=Very Satisfied

Table 6.

Challenges Encountered by Hotels during a Global Health Crisis

Items	f	%
1. The hotel has an area for symptomatic guests.	27	12.80
2. The hotel screens existing guests and travel history using a health checklist provided by the DOH.	26	12.30
3. The hotel provides guests with reminder cards (e.g., no food sharing, proper disposal of used PPE, mingling with occupants, and proper handwashing).	22	10.40
4. The hotel encourages online payment methods upon booking.	7	3.80
5. The hotel has Grab-to-Go stations (e.g., take-out counters).	7	3.30
6. The hotel has sanitation stations that are set up and accessible to guests.	6	3.30
7. The hotel's recreational areas are operating but with strict observance of DOH-prescribed minimum public health standards.	6	2.80
8. The hotel has official up-to-date information that is available at the reception desk about travel, including local destinations that are identified by DOH as high risk of spreading the disease.	5	2.40
9. The hotel rooms are set up to allow convenient in-room dining for guests.	5	2.40
10. The hotel ensures prompt action in cleaning rooms after each use of guests.	5	2.40
11. The hotel undergoes body temperature checking and shoe disinfection for guests undertaken by a qualified health or medical staff or trained hotel personnel.	4	1.90
12. The hotel provides management policies on room occupancy, dining, and use of public areas to ensure safety.	4	1.90
13. The hotel's restaurant and dining facilities have proper airflow direction/air-conditioned ventilation.	4	1.90
14. The hotel ensures an adequate supply of soap, alcohol-based sanitizers, toilet paper, and paper towels in the restroom	3	1.40
15. The hotel ensures confidentiality in the reporting of individuals within the hotel.	3	1.40
16. The hotel's food and beverage personnel strictly always observe proper hygiene.	2	0.90
17. The hotel dining tables are arranged at least more than 1 meter apart.	2	0.90
18. The hotel's function venues have limited capacities to ensure physical distancing.	2	0.90

19. The hotel observed physical distancing measures.	1	0.50
20. The hotel has 70% solution alcohol, sanitizer, and tissue paper/paper towel available at the concierge.	1	0.50
21. The hotel has a policy that prohibits discrimination against guests.	1	0.50

Figures

Conceptual Framework

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